

Original Article

Effect of Replacing Corn Silage with Canola Silage on Feed Intake, Nutrient Digestibility, Milk Yield, and Thyroid Hormones of Lactating Dairy Cows

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Providing good quality forage in dairy cattle diet is vital for the dairy farm industry. Canola forage was newly added to dairy cows' diet in Iran. The present study aimed to determine the effects of replacing corn silage with canola silage on feed intake, apparent digestibility, milk yield, milk composition, and thyroid hormone levels of dairy cattle in Mashhad, Iran.

Materials and methods: Nine Holstein cows were used in this study and were allocated in a 3×3 change over Latin square design study. The trial consisted of 3 periods, each lasting for 20 days. The first 15 days were considered an adaptation period. Experimental diets were formulated to provide 33% of the total dry matter (DM) as forage. Canola silage was substituted with corn silage at levels of 0, 50, and 100% of DM.

Results: Dietary concentrations of neutral detergent fiber (NDF) and acid detergent fiber increased when corn silage was replaced by canola silage. Replacing corn silage with canola silage caused a significant decrease in DMI. The apparent digestibility of DM and crude protein were not affected by dietary replacement of corn silage with canola silage; however, organic matter and digestibility of NDF decreased significantly. When corn silage was replaced by canola silage, there were no significant changes in milk yield, fat corrected milk, and milk composition in the investigated cattle, but milk protein changed significantly. The results indicated that 50% substitution of canola silage caused higher milk protein. Rumen fluid pH and its ammonia nitrogen concentration increased significantly in experimental animals. The concentrations of T₃ and T₄ decreased, whereas blood urea nitrogen concentration increased by dietary replacement of corn silage with canola silage.

Conclusion: Canola silage can be substituted with corn silage, and feeding canola silage can be beneficial in some aspects.

1. Introduction

Providing good quality forage in dairy cattle diet is vital for the dairy farm industry¹. Low rain in the last decade has led to a decline in forage production in some semitropical countries, such as Iran². On the other hand, Iran's government planned to increase vegetable oil production, which has increased canola cultivation over the past decade^{2,3}. Canola is one of the oilseed plants that belong to the *Brassica* species⁴. A decreased environmental temperature or acute damage by pests

makes canola cultivation difficult⁵. In this situation, most farmers eliminate damaged canola forage by burning or burying it in the ground. In this condition, there is a question about the possibility of utilizing canola forage in ruminant nutrition. Some studies indicated the nutrient composition of canola silage and its positive effects on dairy cattle performance⁶⁻⁸. Moreover, a study on the effects of adding different levels of rapeseed (canola seed) silage on the diet of beef cattle indicated that tract

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digestibility and NDF were greater in high glucosinolate rapeseed varieties⁹. Given those mentioned above, the current study aimed to determine the effects of substituting corn silage with canola silage on feed intake and apparent digestibility of nutrients, milk yield, and milk composition.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Ethical approval

All animals were treated by the regulations on the guidelines of the Iranian Council of Animal Care (1995), and the experiment was approved by the Iranian Ministry of Agriculture (experimental permission no. 1828).

2.2. Experimental design

In the current study, 9 Holstein dairy cows with a mean parity of 2.5 (mean \pm SD), mean body weight of 556 kg (mean \pm SD), days in milk (DIM) of 89.3 ± 21.19 (mean \pm SD), and milk yield of 41.7 ± 4.0 kg/ d (mean \pm SD) were allocated in a 3 \times 3 change over Latin square design study. This study contained three periods, each lasting 20 days. The first 15 days of each period were the adaptation period. Every five days, a composite diet sample was collected (4 times during each period). Both corn (Agratech 787, Agra Tech Seeds, Inc., Ashburn GA) and Canola (Hyola-308) were plated in the sandy soil on April 6, 2019, and irrigation was provided to supplement natural rainfall. Corn was chopped and stored in a concrete silo on August 11, 2019; canola was mown on August 4, 2019, and allowed to wilt to approximately 20% DM before being chopped and stored in a concrete stave silo. Diet was offered twice daily as a total mixed ration (TMR) at 1000 and 1500 hours. Forage was 33% DM of the diet (Table 1). The experimental diet was substituted for 0, 50, and 100% with corn silage DM in the present study. Diet samples (0.5 kg) were collected during the experiment and stored at -20°C until analysis. The DM content of the experimental diet was determined by drying in the oven at 55°C for 48 hours¹⁰.

After drying, ingredients and TMR were ground to pass through a 1-mm screen (Wiley mill, Arthur H. Thomas, Philadelphia, PA). Samples were analyzed for DM, CP, ash¹¹, ADF, and NDF¹². Cows were milked twice daily, and milk samples (10 ml) were collected four times (twice in the morning and twice in the evening) in the final two days of each period in the milking paller before milking from all quarters. Milk samples were transferred to the Dairy Laboratory of Mashhad Agricultural Organization, Mashhad, Iran, for nutrient composition analysis using a spectrum analyzer (FT400; Foss North America Inc., Eden Prairie, MN). Blood samples (5 ml) were collected from the jugular vein at the end of the experiment. Tubes were allowed to clot, and serum was centrifuged at 30000 rpm at 4°C for 45 minutes. Blood concentrations of urea nitrogen and glucose were

measured using an enzymatic and colorimetric method by zist shimi analyzing kits, Iran. Thyroid hormone was measured by radioimmunoassay procedure. Fecal samples were collected directly from the rectum in the last five days of each experimental period. Fecal samples of DM, ash, CP, ADF, NDF, and acid-insoluble ash (AIA) were collected and analyzed. Acid-insoluble ash was used as an indicator to determine the apparent digestibility of nutrients¹². Ruminal fluid samples were taken 3 hours after feeding on the last day of each experimental period from the ventral sac of the rumen, and pH was determined. Ruminal fluid samples were preserved by adding 10 ml chloric acid to 10 ml of ruminal fluid and stored at -20°C for further analysis.

Table 1. Ingredient and chemical composition of dairy cows' diets

Composition	Diet		
	Canola silage replaced corn silage (TMR DM%)		
	0%	5% (% of DM)	10%
Corn silage	10	5	0
Canola silage	0	5	10
Alfalfa hay	23	23	23
Corn	20	20	20
Barley	10	10	10
Beat pulp	2	2	2
Soybean meal	6	6	6
Canola meal	8.5	8.5	8.5
Cotton seed meal	8	8	8
Wheat bran	3	3	3
Cotton seed	7	7	7
Fat powder	1.5	1.5	1.5
Mineral and Vitamin supplement	0.3	0.3	0.3
Calcium carbonate	0.5	0.5	0.5
Salt	0.2	0.2	0.2
Chemical			
DM (%)	74.63	69.44	64.93
NEL (Mcal/K)	1.6	1.6	1.61
CP (%) of DM	18	18.3	18.6
RUP (%) of DM	6	6.5	7
RDP (%) of DM	12	11.8	11.6
NFC (%) of DM	41.3	40.6	39.8
NDF (%) of DM	33.2	33.6	33.9
ADF (%) of DM	21	21.6	22.1
EE (%)	5.3	5.4	5.5
Ca (%)	0.9	0.9	0.9
P (%)	0.5	0.5	0.5

Samples of strained ruminal fluid were thawed and centrifuged at 30,000 g for 20 minutes at 4°C and supernatants were analyzed for NH₃ using the Kjeldahl method¹².

2.3. Statistical analysis

The resulting data were statistically analyzed using the linear model in the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS 16, Chicago, USA). Tukey test was chosen to determine the mean significant differences between treatments. The $p < 0.05$ was considered a significant difference between the experimental treatments.

3. Results and Discussion

The nutrient content of corn silage and canola silage is presented in Table 2. The DM content of corn silage was higher than canola silage ($p < 0.05$). Concentrations of CP in corn silage were lower than in canola silage, but NDF and ADF contents of canola silage were higher ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1 demonstrates the composition of the experimental diets. The results showed a decrease in the DM content of the diet by replacing corn silage with canola silage. Moreover, there was an increase in the CP, NDF, and ADF of experimental diets, which might be due to the higher fiber content of canola silage, compared to corn silage⁷⁻¹³. The DMI values between experimental treatments were significantly different (Table 3). The DMI decreased by increasing the substitution level of corn silage with canola silage ($p < 0.05$). *Brassica* forage contains 80-95% water, limiting DMI from the gut fill effect¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The NDF content in the ruminants' diet is an important chemical predictor of DMI¹⁷. The DMI has a positive correlation with NDF concentration and limits food intake^{10,18}. Therefore, an increase in the NDF content of diets caused by substituting corn silage with canola silage can effectively limit DMI^{9,19}. Nutrient apparent digestibility of diets is presented in Table 3. The dietary replacement of corn silage with canola silage did not affect the digestibility of DM and CP. However, the apparent digestibility of NDF ($p < 0.05$) and OM ($p < 0.05$) decreased as a result of canola silage replacement. The findings of a study on feed intake and apparent digestibility of diet supplemented with *Brassica* hay in Lambs showed that hay plus tyfon (*Brassica*) diets exhibited negative associations in apparent digestibility of NDF, and ADF⁹. Likewise, the results of the current study indicated that canola, similar to tyfon decreased the apparent digestibility of NDF.

The current study showed an increase in rumen pH and NH₃-N concentration in the dietary replacement of corn silage with canola silage ($p < 0.05$, Table 3). Chewing activity increases by intake of forage due to its fibers³. Chewing time increase with an increase in the proportion of NDF in the diet that stimulates saliva secretion²⁰. Saliva contains half the bicarbonate entering the rumen that helps to buffer the acids produced during fermentation^{18,19,21}.

It is suggested that an increase in diet NDF content by replacing canola silage with corn silage is associated with increased ruminal pH value. The substitution of corn

Table 2. Chemical composition of corn silage and canola silage

Composition	Silage	
	Corn	Canola
DM (%)	30.00 ± 1.70 ^a	19.50 ± 1.17 ^b
OM (%) of DM	94.20 ± 1.20	90.00 ± 1.69
CP (%) of DM	7.17 ± 0.528 ^a	16.57 ± 0.67 ^b
EE (%)	3.00 ± 0.28	4.80 ± 0.37
NDF (%) of DM	43.60 ± 1.07 ^a	50.30 ± 2.29 ^b
ADF (%) of DM	29.00 ± 1.40 ^a	38.00 ± 1.20 ^b

DM: Dry matter; OM: Organic matter, CP: Crude protein, EE: Ether extract, NDF: Neutral detergent fiber, ADF: Acid detergent fiber, ^{ab} Superscript letters in rows show significant differences in the groups ($p < 0.05$)

Table 3. Feed intake, nutrient digestibility and rumen fermentative parameters of primiparous cows fed diets containing different proportions of canola silage and corn silage

Item	Diet			SE
	Corn silage replaced with canola silage (TMR DM percent)			
	0%	5%	10%	
DMI (kg/d)	21.60 ^a	20.90 ^{ab}	20.38 ^b	
Apparent digestibility (%)				
DM	74.73	73.38	73.05	0.76
OM	72.71 ^a	71.37 ^a	68.12 ^b	1.04
CP	67.42	64.80	63.92	1.26
NDF	59.46 ^a	58.53 ^a	54.32 ^b	1.37
Rumen fluid pH	6.43	6.55	6.56	0.076
Rumen NH ₃ -N (mg/dl)	20.97	20.99	22.27	2.22

^{ab} Superscript letters in rows show significant differences in the groups ($p < 0.05$), DM: Dry matter; OM: Organic matter, CP: Crude protein; NDF: Neutral detergent fiber, SE: Standard error

silage with canola silage enhanced the CP content of diets, increasing ruminal NH₃-N concentration.

Replacing corn silage with canola silage did not change milk yield, FCM (4%), and milk chemical composition (Table 4), but protein in the group where 50% of corn silage was replaced with canola silage was higher than in other treatments ($p < 0.05$).

Blood glucose and BUN concentration were influenced as canola silage replaced corn silage (Table 5). Replacement of corn silage with canola silage results in an increase in diets CP content so it can be effective in enhancing BUN concentration²². Increased content, solubility, and degradability of dietary protein can lead to increased ammonia concentrations in the rumen, resulting in high blood BUN concentrations.

It is indicated that increasing rumen propionate concentration as a result of fermentation of tyfon (*Brassica*) forage carbohydrates enhances blood glucose concentration²³.

Serum T₃ and T₄ concentrations were affected by increasing substitution levels of corn silage with canola silage (Table 5). Glucosinolate contains *Brassica* has a negative impact on thyroid gland function by interfering with iodine uptake²⁴⁻²⁶.

Table 4. Lactation performance of primiparous cows fed diets containing different proportions of canola silage and corn silage

Composition	Diet			SE
	Corn silage replaced by canola silage (TMR DM percent)			
	0%	5%	10%	
Milk, (kg/d)	36.48	35.64	36.04	0.425
4% FCM, (kg/d)	32.16	31.59	32.25	0.593
TS (%)	11.73	11.77	11.81	0.091
CP (%)	3.03 ^a	2.87 ^b	3.00 ^a	0.044
Fat (%)	3.21	3.24	3.29	0.083
Lactose (%)	4.75	4.77	4.77	0.053
SNF (%)	8.52	8.47	8.51	0.08

^{ab} Superscript letters in rows show significant differences in the groups ($p < 0.05$), FCM: Fat corrected milk, TS: Total solid, CP: Crude protein, SNF: Solids non-fat, SE: Standard error

Table 5. Blood glucose, BUN, and thyroid hormones concentration of dairy cows fed diets containing different proportions of canola silage and corn silage

Item	Diet			SE
	Corn silage replaced by canola silage (TMR DM percent)			
	0%	50%	100%	
Glucose (mg/dl)	52.55 ^b	53.88 ^{ab}	56.77 ^a	2.19
BUN (mg/dl)	15.21 ^b	17.71 ^{ab}	19.79 ^a	1.41
T3 (ng/dl)	124.55 ^a	111.27 ^{ab}	99.44 ^b	9.4
T4 (µg/dl)	5.76 ^a	5.60 ^a	4.96 ^b	0.23

^{ab} Superscript letters in rows show significant differences in the groups ($p < 0.05$), BUN: Blood urea nitrogen, T3: Triiodothyronine, T4: Tetraiodothyronine, SE: Standard error

A study reported a reduction in T₄ concentration and an enhancement in T₃ concentration in lambs due to diets containing rape²⁷.

Seeds are the major source of glucosinolates in the canola plant⁷. Although in this study the concentrations of glucosinolates did not measure. It seems that the canola pods in canola forage can increase glucosinolates concentration in diets as canola silage was replaced with corn silage. It diminished the levels of T₄ and T₃ in cows treated with 100% canola silage.

4. Conclusion

The moisture content of corn silage exceeded that of canola silage. The corn silage's CP (crude protein) was lower than canola silage. In contrast, the NDF (neutral detergent fiber) and ADF (acid detergent fiber) content in canola silage surpassed that of corn silage. Corn silage can be used as a substitute for canola silage, and incorporating canola silage into feed can be advantageous in certain aspects. However, the high fiber content in canola silage may limit dry matter intake (DMI). Therefore, further research is needed to determine the appropriate application of canola silage in dairy cattle diets.

Declarations

Competing interests

There is no conflict of interest.

Authors' contribution

The final manuscript draft was reviewed by all authors, who also approved it.

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Ethical considerations

Ethical issues (including plagiarism, consent to publish, misconduct, data fabrication and falsification, double publication and submission, and redundancy) have been checked by all the authors.

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References

- Arce-Cordero JA, Paula EM, Daniel JLP, Silva LG, Broderick GA, and Faciola AP. Effects of neutral detergent fiber digestibility estimation method on calculated energy concentration of canola meals from 12 Canadian processing plants. *J Anim Sci*. 2021;99(11) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.1093/jas/skab309>
- Taravat A, Rajaei M, and Emadodin I. Urbanization dynamics of Tehran city (1975–2015) using artificial neural networks, *Journal of Maps*. 2017; 13:1, 24-30, DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.1080/17445647.2017.1305300>
- Mansouri Daneshvar MR, Ebrahimi M, and Nejadsoleymani H. An overview of climate change in Iran: facts and statistics. *Environ Syst Res*. 2019; (8). 7 DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.1186/s400680190135-3>
- Keim JP, Daza J, Beltrán I, Balocchi OA, Pulido RG, Sepúlveda-Varas P, Pacheco D, Berthiaume R. Milk production responses, rumen fermentation, and blood metabolites of dairy cows fed increasing concentrations of forage rape (*Brassica napus* ssp. *Biennis*). *J Dairy Sci*. 2020; 103, (10): 9054-9066. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2020-18785>
- Broderick GA. Utilization of protein in red clover and alfalfa silages by lactating dairy cows and growing lambs. *J Dairy Sci*. 2018; 101(2): 1190-1205. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.3168/jds.2017-13690>
- Mi H, Ren A, Zhu J, Ran T, Shen W, Zhou C, Zhang B, Tan Z. Effects of different protein sources on nutrient disappearance, rumen fermentation parameters and microbiota in dual-flow continuous culture system. *AMB Express*. 2022; 12(1): 15. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.1186/s13568-022-01358-1>
- Paula EM, Broderick GA, and Faciola AP. Effects of replacing soybean meal with canola meal for lactating dairy cows fed 3 different ratios of alfalfa to corn silage. *J Dairy Sci*. 2020; 103(2): 1463-1471. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.3168/jds.2019-16947>
- Paula EM, da Silva LG, Brandao VLN, Dai X, Faciola AP. Feeding Canola, Camelina, and Carinata Meals to Ruminants. *Animals (Basel)*. 2019; 9(10): 704. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.3390/ani9100704>
- Lancaster LL, Hunt CW, Miller JC and Auld DL. Effects of rapeseed silage variety and dietary level on digestion and growth performance of beef steers. *J Anim Sci*. 1990. 68: 3812-3820. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.2527/1990.68113812X>
- Badiee A, Naserian AA, Jones G, Razavi SA. Effects of adding corn silage to the diet of dairy calves on the weight gain, dry matter intake, and chemical blood parameters before weaning. *Comp Clin Pathol*. 2022; (31): 23-27. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00580-021-03291-4>
- Association of Official Analytical Chemists International. 1990. *Official Methods of Analysis*. Vol. I. 15th ed. AOAC, Arlington, VA.
- Van Keulen J, and Young BA. Evaluation of acid insoluble ash as a natural marker in ruminant digestibility studies. *J Anim Sci*. 1977; 44: 282.
- Phesatcha K, Phesatcha B, Wanapat M, Cherdthong A. Roughage to Concentrate Ratio and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Inclusion Could

- Modulate Feed Digestion and In Vitro Ruminal Fermentation. *Vet Sci*. 2020; 7(4): 151. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.3390/vetsci7040151>
14. Guillard K, and Allinson DW. Yield and nutrient content of summer- and fall-grown forage Brassica crops. *Can J Plant Sci*. 1988; 68: 721. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjps88-085>
 15. Guillard K, and Allinson DW, and Hough RL. Performance of sheep grazing fall-grown tyfon. *Appl Agric Res*. 1988; 3: 86.
 16. Higginbotham GE, Torabi M, and Huber JT. Influence of dietary protein concentration and degradability on performance of lactating cows during hot environmental temperatures. *J Dairy Sci*. 1989; 72: 2554-2564. DOI: [https://www.doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(89\)79396-6](https://www.doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(89)79396-6)
 17. Waldo, D. R. Effect of forage quality on intake and forage concentrate interactions. *J Dairy Sci*. 1986; 69: 617-631. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(86\)80446-5](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(86)80446-5)
 18. Mertens DR. Regulation of forage intake. Pp. 450-493, 1994. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2134/1994.foragequality.c11>
 19. Owens FN, Secrist DS, Hill WJ, and Gill DR. Acidosis in cattle: A review. *J Anim Sci*. 1998; 76: 275-286. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.2527/1998.761275x>
 20. Beauchemin KA. Ingestion and mastication of feed by dairy cattle. *Vet. Clin. North Am. Food Anim Pract*. 1991; 7: 439-463. DOI: [https://www.doi.org/10.1016/s0749-0720\(15\)30794-5](https://www.doi.org/10.1016/s0749-0720(15)30794-5)
 21. Mertens DR. Creating a system for meeting the fiber requirements of dairy cows. *J Dairy Sci*. 1997; 80: 1463-1481. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(97\)76075-2](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(97)76075-2)
 22. Hammond, A. C. 1983. The use of blood urea nitrogen concentration as an indicator of protein status in cattle. *Bovine Practitioner* 18:114-118. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21423/bovine-vol1983no18p114-118>
 23. Cassida KA, Barton BA, Hough RL, Wiedenhoef MH, and Guillardt K. Feed Intake and Apparent Digestibility of Hay-Supplemented Brassica Diets for Lambs. *J Anim Sci*. 1994; 72: 1623-1629. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2527/1994.7261623x>
 24. Barry TN, McDonald RC, and Reid TC. Nutritional evaluation of kale (*Brassica oleracea*) diets. 1. Growth of grazing lambs as affected by time after introduction to the crop, feed allowance and intraperitoneal amino acid supplementation. *J Agric Sci*. 1981a. 96: 257. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002185960006603X>
 25. Barry TN, Duncan SJ, Sadler WA, Millar KR, and Sheppard AD. Iodine metabolism and thyroid hormone relationships in growing sheep fed on kale (*Brassica oleracea*) and ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*-clover (*Trifolium repens*) freshforage diets. *Br J Nutr*. 1983; 49: 241. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1079/bjn19830031>
 26. Barry TN, Reid TC, Millar KR, and Sadler WA. Nutritional evaluation of kale (*Brassica oleracea*) diets. 2. Copper deficiency, thyroid function and selenium status in young cattle and sheep fed kale for prolonged periods. *J Agric Sci*. 1981b; 96: 269. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859600066041>
 27. Lambert MG, Abrams SM, Harpster HW, and Jung GA. Effect of hay substitution on intake and digestibility of forage rape (*Brassica napus*) fed to lambs. *J Anim Sci*. 1987; 65: 1639. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas1987.6561639x>